

**INNOVATIONS IN TECHNOLOGY AND SCIENCE EDUCATION
SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF
INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REGIONS**

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ABSTRACT

In the article, innovative entrepreneurship is one of the requirements of the time, the factors that lead to its implementation, the obstacles that arise in the development of innovative entrepreneurship in the regions, and proposals for their elimination are presented.

KEY WORDS

Innovation, innovative entrepreneurship, classic model of entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

The most important and, at the same time, the most difficult task of entrepreneurship is to search for new ideas and implement them, because in this case, the entrepreneur needs not only creative thinking and finding new solutions, but also perspective thinking and the ability to see the needs of the future society. Innovation is one of the important directions of entrepreneurship, an innovative form of new thinking.

METHODS

In accordance with international standards, the term "innovation" is reflected in the "Frascati Manual". According to the Frascati Manual (a document adopted by The

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development in Frascati, Italy in 1993), innovation is defined as a new or improved product, technological process or new approach to social service delivery brought to the market as a result of innovative activity accepted.[1]

Today, the description of technological innovations is based on the international standards adopted in Oslo in 1992 (Oslo Guide). These standards cover new products and new processes, as well as their significant technological changes. This document describes the types of innovations as follows:

- product innovation (new or improved goods and services);
- process (significant changes in production technology);
- marketing (a new method of marketing, including changes in product design or packaging, its placement, changes in the market and price segment);
- organizational (new organizational methods in business practice, methods of forming new jobs or establishing external relations)[2]

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and Eurostat offer the following definitions for the term "innovation": " **innovation** - it represents the introduction of some new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, new marketing methods or new organizational method into practice for consumption, organization of jobs or external relations. [3] Therefore, opening a wide path to innovations, providing them with financial support, is currently considered an important factor in ensuring the economic stability and development of our country. It should be considered that the result of each developed research work, the innovative project should ultimately be its consumer. From the above definition, it should be noted that scientific research and innovation are interrelated activities and there are very different approaches to it.

The term "innovation" as an economic category was introduced to the science in the first decade of the 20th century by the Austrian scientist Joseph Alois Schumpeter (1883-1950), who in his "Theory of Economic Development" (1911) first described

new combinations of changes in development. issues (i.e. innovation issues) and gave a complete description of the innovation process.

Y. Schumpeter identified 5 changes in development:

- 1) Use of new techniques, technological processes or new market supply of production;
- 2) Introduction of new special products;
- 3) Use of new raw materials ;
- 4) Changes in the organization of production and its material and technical support;
- 5) Emergence of new sales markets.

It should be noted that any innovative activity is entrepreneurship, since it is the search for new ideas (and their evaluation, from new products to content); search for necessary resources; creating and managing an enterprise; is based on obtaining material income and personal satisfaction from its result. However, not every business can be innovative, only those that provide an opportunity to use business income and diffusion of innovative products as a result of creation can be called innovation. Organizations carrying out innovative activities are innovative business entities. Accordingly, two models of entrepreneurship are distinguished.

The first model is classical entrepreneurship (traditional, productive, outdated) aimed at organizing activities with the maximum return from the available resources at the disposal of the entrepreneurial organization. In the classic model of entrepreneurship, the concept of production growth is formed, its implementation requires state support, time for activities carried out at the expense of external subsidizing factors for the entrepreneurial firm. In addition, its internal reserves are also used to increase the efficiency of the company.

The second model is innovative entrepreneurship, which implies new ways of enterprise development, allows to talk about innovation or the concept of growth. Innovative entrepreneurship is based entirely on innovation, so the result of such

activity can be a new product or a new product with mainly new characteristics and features, or new technologies. Usually, any form of entrepreneurial activity includes a small innovation opportunity, for example, the introduction of new methods of organizing the production of quality products from the organization to manage production, or using new technology. It can be carried out by the production or export of traditional products to the market, as well as by the use of some new elements or methods related to the organization of production, technical elements of production or changes in the description of product quality from production.

RESULTS

Innovative entrepreneurship development necessity the following factors with describes:

	Affecting factors
1	- increasing the role of the intensive factor of production, which helps to apply innovations in all spheres of economic activity;
2	- the need to significantly reduce the time of creation, to master new techniques, to raise the technical level of production, to mass develop creativity of inventors and rationalizers;
3	- increase in spending and decrease in the economic indicators of enterprises in the adoption of new products;
4	- with the objective need for rapid implementation of new techniques and technology, etc.
5	- the important role of science in increasing the efficiency of development and the introduction of new techniques;
6	- the uniqueness of the scientific and technical production process, expressed by the uncertainty of the results, the multiplicity of research, the existence of risks and the possibility of achieving negative results;
7	- in the violent spiritual obsolescence of equipment and technology;

The development of innovative entrepreneurship depends on innovations by consumers, the development of the scientific and technical potential of the national economy, and the activities of venture firms and investors financing risky innovative activities. Based on this, the following obstacles may arise in the development of innovative entrepreneurship of the regions:

Problems and obstacles in the development of innovative entrepreneurship

•important needs of entrepreneurs in marketing research are related to advertising, marketing and sales advice[4]

Limited resources for the development of innovative entrepreneurship, insufficient development of financial means of supporting small and medium-sized businesses;

•Organizations are not ready to switch to an innovative business model and do not understand the need for the growth of companies, to switch to innovative production. [5]

•Ignoring payment of fees and copyright support, which automatically leads to counterfeiting, which leads to the outflow of ideas and experts

personnel issues

•imperfection of legislation regulating and stimulating national innovative activity [6];

•consumers of innovation - the problem of communication between research carried out by public institutions and private companies [7].

DISCUSSION

As a solution to the problems in the development of innovative entrepreneurship in the regions, the following is proposed:

- Use of marketing analysis and audit consulting services;
- Application of directions for use of alternative resources;
- Establishing the use of crowdfunding, business angels, grants in financing innovative activities;
- Establishing mutual cooperation of innovative entrepreneurial activities with higher education institutions;

- Improvement of regulatory and legal documents;
- Forming and presenting the need for specialists to higher education institutions;
- Making suggestions on the improvement of legal documents;
- Creation of platforms where public-private companies meet consumers.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that enterprises engaged in innovative entrepreneurship have high potential. In this regard, it is necessary to encourage the creation of innovation-oriented enterprises, as well as to develop and expand the activities of existing innovation-active enterprises.

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